

**ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND MIDDLE CLASS FORMATION OF
UZBEKISTAN**

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The economic development of Uzbekistan during the years of independence and the formation of the middle class are one of the important aspects of the socio-economic life of the country. In this thesis, we analyze the relationship between a country's economic growth and the development of the middle class.

The main part

The economic development of Uzbekistan during the years of independence and the formation of the middle class was a complex and multifaceted process, which left a deep mark on the socio-economic life of the country. In the early years of independence, Uzbekistan faced complex tasks such as transition to a market economy, implementation of economic reforms and formation of a new economic system. During this process, the country's leadership chose a unique development path called the "Uzbek model", which was aimed at combining economic growth and social stability.

One of the main directions of economic reforms was the process of privatization. This process was aimed at liberalizing the economy by transferring state property to the private sector. Professor R. Muqimov stated that "The process of privatization was carried out gradually in Uzbekistan, which made it possible to prevent sharp social upheavals and gradually form a class of private owners" [1]. As a result of this process, the number of small and medium-sized business entities increased significantly, which in turn created the basis for the formation of the middle class.

Development of entrepreneurship and improvement of the investment environment is one of the priorities of the economic policy of Uzbekistan. Laws and decrees adopted in recent years are aimed at supporting business activities, reducing bureaucratic obstacles and creating favorable conditions for foreign investors. Economist S. As Gulyamov noted, "By improving the investment environment, Uzbekistan not only attracts foreign capital, but also increases the activity of local entrepreneurs" [2].

The formation of the middle class is an important indicator of the economic development of Uzbekistan. One of the main factors of this process is the development of the education system and the training of qualified personnel. During the years of independence, fundamental reforms in the field of education were carried out in Uzbekistan, including the introduction of a 12-year compulsory education system, the number of higher education institutions was increased, and international cooperation was strengthened. Sociologist D. In his research, Rahmonov concludes as follows: "As a result of reforms in the field of education, the number of highly qualified specialists in Uzbekistan increased, which led to the

qualitative growth of the middle class" [3].

The development of small and medium-sized businesses is of particular importance in the formation of the middle class. The programs adopted by the government of Uzbekistan to support small and medium-sized businesses, tax incentives and financial support measures have led to the rapid development of this sector. Economist A. As Vahabov noted, "The share of small and medium-sized business entities in GDP increased from 31 percent in 2000 to 55 percent by 2020, which indicates the strengthening of the middle class in the country" [4].

Changes in income distribution and the improvement of the social protection system also have a great impact on the formation of the middle class. The social policy implemented by the government of Uzbekistan is aimed at increasing the income of the population, reducing poverty and reducing social inequality. In this regard, the "Unified Register of Social Protection" system adopted in recent years is of particular importance. Social policy expert N. As stated by Karimova, "The new social protection system allows precise and targeted support of the population in need of assistance, which expands the possibilities of transition to the middle class" [5].

The role of the middle class in economic development is extremely important. First, the middle class is the main force in stimulating domestic demand and expanding the consumer market. As their purchasing power increases, local production also develops, which ensures economic growth. Second, representatives of the middle class often serve as the main driving force of innovative activity and technological progress. They strive to introduce new technologies to their businesses and create innovative products. Third, a strong middle class will help

ensure social and political stability in the country, as they will have an interest in maintaining their own prosperity.

However, Uzbekistan still has a number of problems that need to be solved. The process of transition to the digital economy requires the continuous improvement of their skills while creating new opportunities for the representatives of the middle class. Economist B. As Begalov noted, "In the process of digital transformation, representatives of the middle class face great difficulties in acquiring new skills and adapting to digital technologies" [6].

The need to increase global competitiveness remains an urgent issue for the economy of Uzbekistan. In this regard, development of innovative activities, increase of production efficiency and strengthening of export potential are of particular importance. Professor M. According to Sharifhojaev, "in order to increase the global competitiveness of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to deepen not only economic, but also institutional reforms" [7].

Reducing regional differences and ensuring inclusive growth is one of the important directions of Uzbekistan's economic policy. In this regard, measures such as comprehensive regional development programs, infrastructure projects, and the creation of special economic zones are being implemented by the government. Economist Sh. As Mustafakulov noted, "By reducing regional disparities, we ensure not only economic growth, but also social justice, which is an important condition for the sustainable development of the middle class" [8].

Summary

The economic development of Uzbekistan and the formation of the middle class are interrelated processes. A country's steady economic growth leads to an

expanding middle class, which in turn further stimulates economic development. Understanding and managing the interaction of these two processes is important in Uzbekistan's future development strategy.

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